

BIOINSPIRED NANOSTRUCTURED GLASS FIBRE SURFACE AND COMPOSITE INTERPHASE

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1 Introduction

A natural protective covering such as the skin or the shell is a multifunctional design providing an animal's first line of defense against all the hardships, site of the sense of touch and the optical colour appearance. To maximize survivability, the evolution of skin coverings of pangolins and fishes with a flexible multilayer of overlapping tough scales, provides a protective layer against numerous environmental threats (i.e. complex mechanical stresses, wear, moisture), together with mechanical support, and other multiple sensing purposes. The smallest building blocks in many nature materials are generally on the nanometer length scale, which is selected to ensure optimum strength and maximum tolerance of flaws [1]. Besides strong and resilient, the multiple nanostructured layers of nacreous shells create structural colours, appearing iridescent without the use of pigments [2,3].

It provides us with inspiration to develop organic–inorganic nanostructured composite surfaces for enhanced durability and additional functions of traditional materials. Research in this area has progressed so fast, e.g., nanocomposites with maximum tolerance of flaws [1], solid lubrication coatings [4], smart responsive skins [5], human–like sensing materials [6] and coloured polymer films [7]. While most of the studies are devoted to bulk solids, thin films or powders, the functionalization of traditional fibres (i.e., the most commonly used for reinforcements: glass fibres) or composite interphases are now drawing more and more attention from interdisciplinary fields. To develop such hierarchical structures on glass fibre surface, it is most interesting to select the small building blocks on the nanometer scale, such as graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs). Experimentally, many graphene characteristics have exceeded those

obtained in any other material, with some reaching theoretically predicted limits: room–temperature electron mobility of $2.5 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$; a Young's modulus of 1 TPa and intrinsic strength of 130 GPa; very high thermal conductivity above $3,000 \text{ WmK}^{-1}$ [8-11]. The major advantage of graphenes as sensors is their multi–functionality, which offers unique opportunities for a single device being used in multidimensional measurements (for example, strain, gas environment, pressure and magnetic field). The combination of transparency, elasticity and conductivity will find use in flexible electronics, protective coatings and barrier films; and the list of such combinations for composite applications is continuously growing. It has been demonstrated that graphite flakes thicker than one monolayer can also provide a significant level of reinforcement in composites [12]. However, nanostructured fibre surface with carbon particles/polymer is difficult because it encounters poor mixing and agglomeration as well as wetting problem for high volume fraction of the strongly hydrophobic particles. Compared to carbon nanotubes, it would be challenging for graphenes to be deposited onto glass fibre surface, due to the high value of specific surface area and layer structure of graphenes. In addition, recent studies have raised concerns regarding various chemically functionalized and exfoliated GNPs generally showing inferior thermal/electrical conductivity and mechanical properties [13]. Thus, their full power will only be realized in novel treatments, which are designed specifically.

Here, inspired by the natural protective coverings, we report the use of graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in glass fibre surface coatings and in turn composite interphases to integrate optical, mechanical and electrical

functionalities along the line of our recent works [14-16].

2 Experimental

2.1 Surface Nanostructuring Glass Fibres

The alkali-resistant glass fibres (ARG) with an average diameter of 17 μm were made at our institute by a continuous spinning process. We used commercial GNPs (xGnP-M-15, XG Science, USA) and carboxyl functionalized multi-walled CNTs (NC-3101, Nanocyl S.A., Belgium) produced via the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process. The GNPs have average thickness of 6 nm and surface area of 135 m^2/g and the CNTs have average diameter of 9.5 nm and average length of 1.5 μm . We developed a simple 'adhesion-orientation' method to fabricate the GNPs/epoxy-glass fibres. Specifically, the single fibre initially imbedded in the epoxy resin/hardener mixture was drawn between two soft substrates where the GNPs were distributed in 'dry' stage without the need of a solvent, thus, the GNPs were shifted to the fibre surface by adhesive force and in turn the platelets were oriented along fibre surface direction by fluid deformation and friction/shear forces. Based on the AFM images, our initial approach achieved coverage rate of fibre surface by GNPs is about 20-50%, which could be further improved when the process is repeated layer by layer. To avoid complex effects from temperature variation, a room-temperature curing epoxy (UHU plus 300, UHU GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) was used for the GNPs coatings. The epoxy resins for CNTs coatings were commercial products DGEBA resin (EPR L20, Momentive Specialty Chemicals, Germany) with hardener EPH960. To further achieve conducting networks with homogeneous and continuous distribution of carbon nanoparticles (GNPs or CNTs) on the glass fibre surface, the simple dip-coating method is used. To avoid inferior effect to electrical conductivity from the conventional graphite oxide reduction method, we generated graphene nanoplates (GNPs) based on a liquid-phase exfoliation graphite method [17]. A stable diffusion GNPs in solution is achieved through the bath sonication and centrifugation process, where the sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) is dissolved in Millipore water. Through a layer-by-layer dip coating method,

multilayer formation of GNPs on glass fibre surface is realised. To deposit conducting CNT networks onto glass fibre surfaces, similarly, the glass fibres were dipped into a stabilized and individualized multiwalled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) aqueous dispersion as reported previously in detail by us [14,15].

2.2 Characterization of Functional Glass Fibres and Composites

The fibre surface morphologies were studied using atomic force microscopy (AFM, a Digital Instruments D3100, USA), scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM Ultra 55, Carl Zeiss SMT AG, Germany), and optical microscope (Keyence Corporation, VH-Z100R).

The abrasive wear resistance of a single GNP-glass fibre was determined by the relative friction displacement (sliding between two surfaces) S , where it contacts and abrades over the surface of abrasive paper (p2500 SiC, Buehler GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany) on a rotating rod up to the fibre breakage. Using the Favigraph semiautomatic fibre tensile tester (Textechno, Germany) equipped with a 1 N force cell, the friction force of a single fibre sliding over the abrasive paper on a cylindrical surface at angle of wrap $\pi/2$, initial tension of 1.96 cN, and cross velocity 1 mm/min was measured.

The technique applied to operate and measure the electrical properties of a single GNP-glass fibre or CNT-glass fibre has been realized, in which one fibre bridges two electrodes with Au layer at small gap distances varied from 0.5 to 3.5 mm. Approximately, ten fibre specimens for each condition were measured. Four-point conductivity measurements were carried out with a Keithley 2000 multimeter, to *in-situ* monitor the DC electrical resistance changes for the single CNT-glass fibres. In order to detect piezoresistive effects, the electrical resistance was recorded simultaneously when the mechanical tensile stress/strain was performed by the Favigraph semiautomatic fibre tensile tester. The experiments of the resistance changing with the temperature for the single glass fibre or the fibre imbedded in cured epoxy resin were carried out in a hot-stage (Linkam LTS350 Heating/Freezing, UK) from $-150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a heating rate of 1 K min^{-1} in a nitrogen atmosphere. The composites with CNT weight fraction of 1.45 wt% were used for cross-sectional analysis after mechanical polishing.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Nanostructured Surface of Glass Fibre

We first attempted to use the ‘adhesion–orientation’ process to make GNPs/epoxy–glass fibres with bioinspired protective coverings. When a glass fibre was immersed into epoxy solution and drawn out, a string of epoxy drops formed on the fibre due to the Rayleigh instability [18] of the polymer solution (see Fig. 1). In general, the contact angle is affected by the surface chemistry and geometry at the contact line. A marginal increase in the contact angles of the epoxy drops on the fibre surfaces with either GNPs or CNTs was found, in comparison to those without carbon nanoparticles, which is directly related to the hydrophobic nature of the nanoparticles. In order to overcome this problem, our strategy makes use of the friction/shear by drawing out the fibre from epoxy and in turn sliding over soft substrates covered with thin layers of GNPs. Specifically, the GNPs were attached to the thin epoxy fluid undergoing a shear deformation, associated orientation/self–assembly processes cause the GNP platelets along the fibre surface. As shown in Fig. 1, it could efficiently remove aggregated epoxy without drop formed. Evidence was revealed by the AFM phase image that highly random nanoplatelets run relatively parallel each other along the fibre axis resulting an anisotropic aligned surface covering, although the process does not introduce very smooth topography ($R_q = 24 \text{ nm}$ in $9 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^2$). These structural features give rise to interestingly optical and mechanical functions as detailed below.

The fibre coated by GNPs basically turned dark grey, which could be explained by the optical absorption of graphene layers to be proportional to the number of layers, each absorbing 2.3% over the visible spectrum [19]. It is interestingly observed that different colors also emerge from the fibre surface subjected to either sunlight or white light from optical microscope (Fig. 1. center). Apparently, such optical phenomenon is not formed by the interaction of light with a dye, but by the diffraction of light from the GNPs/epoxy layers containing the aforementioned quasiperiodic structure. As different wavelengths of light interact with this structure with similar length scale based on the principles of structural colour, they are diffracted in different directions, leading to the iridescences on the fibre surface.

3.2 Abrasion Resistance

The bio–inspired approaches for the manufacture of novel GNPs/epoxy surface structures hierarchically laminated on the nanometer length scale not only exemplify optical colour appearance, but also emphasize maximum tolerance of friction. To provide better protection against scrapes is the second reason for applying GNPs on fibre surface. We characterised the abrasion resistance of single glass fibres by using the friction displacement on the abrasive paper until the fibre breakage occurs. Fig. 2a shows that the GNPs–epoxy systems lead to significant increase up to 200% in the friction displacement. The sample with epoxy coating, however, yields only about 50% improvement. To understand how the nanostructured coatings enhance wear durability, we observe the kinetic friction (or sliding friction) forces and their changes with displacement (Fig. 2b). Although both epoxy and GNPs/epoxy coverages enhance wear resistance, the friction behaviour is quite different. The friction force curve of control smooth glass fibres without any polymer coating is characterized by the lowest value. It shows a little increase at initial stage then remains approximately constant with a calculated coefficient of kinetic friction of 0.39. The increased friction force is attributed to the enhanced mechanical interlocking from a growing roughening the fibre surface with grooves, as confirmed by the AFM image (Fig. 2c). In contrast, the friction force for the epoxy coated fibre decreases monotonically with the friction displacement; the force curve reaches to the same value of that of the control one. The decrease stage can be understood by that abrasive wear occurs when the hard rough SiC surface slides across the softer epoxy surface. As a result of continuously removing epoxy by a cutting or plowing operation, the exposed smooth glass surface subjected to wear increases, causing finally both the friction force and the roughed fibre surface being very similar to the control one (Fig. 2c,d). Interestingly, we found a different tendency for the GNPs/epoxy–glass fibre system. Specifically, its friction force is characterized by the highest value during the whole range of measurement. Friction in general describes the resistance to being dragged or slid along a surface. An increase of friction force at the early stage is caused by increased friction area/contact points, implied more and more GNPs

being exposed and involved in the wear process. Subsequently, the decreased friction force is associated with the partly coating removal till to the friction displacement up to 200 mm. Apparently, the GNPs help to prevent the removal and deformation of the polymer during the subsequent passage of abrasive particles, so that the reduction in friction force strongly associated with the removal of coating layer is observed to significantly slow down. The nanostructured surface has more friction as compared to the control one with smooth glass surface. During the later stage up to a long friction displacement of 400 mm, the almost constant high friction force with a coefficient of kinetic friction 0.49, reveals that part of GNPs/epoxy still remained on the fibre surface and accordingly retarded the wear process (Fig. 2a, c).

The unique anisotropic structural features of GNPs/epoxy with further sufficiently high GNP loadings enable possibly the GNPs to serve as solid lubricant nanoparticles for optimize the three-body abrasive wear, promising additional interesting fibre and composite interphase properties. According to Fig.2d, the gradient anisotropic interphase caused by nano-reinforcements appears to affect strongly micro-crack propagation being far away from the fibre surface. Qualitatively, the nano-reinforcement rich interphase with enhanced mechanical properties protects the original weak fibre/matrix interface from the peak stresses caused by impact/fatigue loading and homogenizes stress distribution within the composite. These results suggest that the GNP-glass fibres could also be attractive reinforcements for further making composites with a gradient anisotropic interphase.

3.3 Multifunctional Sensor

To develop a single glass fibre with multifunctional sensor abilities is the third reason for applying GNPs on fibre surface, since GNPs are extremely sensitive to the environment. Based on a simple layer-by-layer dip-coating deposition method, we developed electrical conducting networks from either GNPs or CNTs on a single glass fibre (Fig. 3a). The SEM images show that the closely packed multilayers of GNPs and highly entangled MWNTs are present on the curved fibre surface. The interconnected both GNP and CNT thin networks on the glass fibre surface show typical thickness of a few tens to a few hundreds of nanometers, which create the

conductive pathway. We conducted the direct electrical resistance measurement of a single glass fibre with functional coverings of GNPs or CNTs (Fig. 3b). The measured DC resistances R of the GNP-glass fibre and CNT-glass fibre are in the ranges of 10^6 – $10^8 \Omega$ and 10^3 – $10^8 \Omega$, respectively. The electric resistance values in general increase with increasing of the length of the fibre (conductor). A large variation in resistance data is observed which is due to the inhomogeneous distribution/connection of nanoparticles on the fibre surface, being extremely more pronounced in the case of CNTs. Hence, the conducting and overlapping GNP layers on the glass fibre through the dip-coating deposition is a feasible route to achieving relatively uniform microstructures in comparison to the CNTs, despite the CNTs networks have apparently higher conductivity. Additional work is needed to validate if the GNP-glass fibres could be reinforcements for further making electrically conducting composites with smart functions.

The present experiments have successfully documented and quantified the first steps of achievement of multifunctional sensing abilities. We investigated whether our conducting GNP-glass fibre is sufficient to show similar piezoresistivity for strain sensing as CNT-glass fibre [14,15]. The correlation of electrical resistance change $\Delta R/R_o$, mechanical stress σ and strain ε was examined to evaluate the piezoresistive behaviour of GNP-glass fibres under stress up to fracture (Fig. 4). We found that the fractional resistance increase ($\Delta R/R_o$) of the fibre increases approximately linearly with tensile strain, which shows very similar behaviour as the CNT-glass fibre and can also be empirically described as:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{GF} \frac{\Delta R}{R_o} + \varepsilon_o \quad (1)$$

where R_o is the initial resistance of the specimen without applying stress, $\Delta R=R-R_o$ is the resistance change, and the parameter, ε_o , refers to the initial strain for piezoresistivity effect of multilayers of GNPs. GF is the strain sensitivity factor (or known as gage factor), i.e, the relative change of resistance to the mechanical strain of strain gage. The GF determined by the regression analysis is 12.1 (Fig. 4a), which show no significant differences to that of the CNT-glass fibre but this value is much higher

than those of metallic strain gages with geometrical piezoresistive effect with usual gage factors of 2.0–3.2. In general, the significant resistance change of GNPs on our glass fibre surface can be attributed to not only the stress dependent resistivity of the GNP geometrical structure, but also the stress dependent change of GNP–GNP interspace, contact area and density (junction point per unit volume), as well as associated tunneling resistance. It should be noted that only below the very small strain level, $\varepsilon_0 \approx 0.1\%$, the GNP structure could not be changed recognizably and the main part of GNPs on fibre surface does not undergo mechanical stress. In other words, the onset strain for piezoresistivity effect is extremely low in comparison with other sensors, so that the single GNP–glass fibre has high sensitivity even under small strain level. It is also important to notice that the final abrupt change in resistance at fibre break implies that the single GNP–glass fibre is able to *in-situ* sensing of damage in real composites at micrometer scale. As a single sensor, the glass fibres with either conducting GNPs or CNTs achieve a basic ability for possibly multifunctional composites.

Further insight into our fibre sensing ability was gained from the response to moisture and its phase transition. The single fibre sensor based on monitoring of resistance change by scanning temperature from $+30^\circ\text{C}$ to -150°C . Overall, the nanostructured glass fibre and its epoxy matrix composites show an inversely proportional relationship of the electric resistance with the temperature and strain (Fig. 5). A negative temperature coefficient (NTC) effect was found, where $\Delta R/R_0$ decrease with increasing temperature, exhibiting a rather non-metallic behaviour. The negative electrical temperature coefficient β can be computed using the following formula:

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \beta T + b \quad (2)$$

where b is the parameter of y-intercept. Importantly, the absorption of water vapor as a result of ambient humidity at temperatures close to freezing conditions leads to a specific non-monotonous temperature dependence of the resistance. As the temperature decreases, intensive precipitation of the water vapor results in an increase in the resistance of GNPs and CNTs due to the adsorption of polar water molecules with the carbon networks, which are

slightly negatively charged. Since GNPs and CNTs usually exhibit a hole transport like p-type semiconductor, the adsorbed water molecules transfer electrons to them and in turn deplete the concentration of holes, resulting in an increase of resistance. Besides, water molecules being adsorbed on the GNP and CNT surfaces create bi-layer, suppressing current flow through GNPs and CNTs and increasing resistance. Upon reaching the maximum peak values (-18°C and -5°C for the GNPs and CNTs, respectively) below the freezing point, a slow decrease in resistance occurs, corresponding to possibly delayed extensive formation of an ice layer. The very thin ice layer is a non-polar that surrounds the carbon surfaces and results in a decrease in resistance. In general, certain properties (i.e. freezing/melting points) of the medium during a phase transition change as a result of some external condition, such as temperature, pressure, and others. The usual feature of water is related to ice having a lower density than liquid water. We consider the moisture diffusion in the GNPs layers, where the higher pressure arising from the compacted and staggered layer structure drives the water molecules into the higher density phase or confines the water molecules making expansion to ice difficult. This might cause the apparently delay of ice layer build-up. Since the detection occurs on a molecular level, interesting properties which are not observed in bulk materials are expected. The detection of ice formation with a thin layer of molecules is made without any significant ice accumulation, which is a significant improvement over conventional ice sensors. A further advantage is that the composites fabricated with the functional fibres exhibit self-diagnosis function as materials found in nature checking for moisture/ice accumulation with respect to long-term storage and environmental change, for example, warning ice buildup on a plane's wing.

4 Summary

The bio-inspired multifunctional single glass fibre sensor is achieved. First, the ‘adhesion–orientation’ or dip-coating approaches are simple and effective processes for the formation of a mechanical protective layer or an electrically semiconducting GNP or CNT network layer on a single glass fibre surface. Second, the nanostructured surface layer serves distinct and multifunctional roles. The novel

GNPs/epoxy surface structures hierarchically laminated on the nanometer length scale not only exemplify optical quasiperiodic colour appearance, but also highlight maximum tolerance of friction. Third, bring traditional reinforcement materials and nanomaterials together, the GNP–glass fibre or CNT–glass fibre can be used as a single sensor device in multidimensional measurements. As *in situ* multifunctional sensors, both fibres show stress/strain, temperature, and moisture dependence in their electrical conductivity; they are capable of detecting piezoresistive effects, very small amount of water vapor, as well as its phase transition. The single GNP–glass fibre shows a higher sensitivity than the CNT–glass fibre. Since a large market exists in bringing extra functionality to composites, the nanostructured surface and interphase with high sensitivity to environmental factors suggest that their full power will be realised more rapidly in novel functional composite applications.

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Fig. 1. Optical microscopic observation of epoxy drops (left) and friction/shear introduced functional coverings of GNPs/epoxy on a glass fibre (center, scale bars, 20 μm). AFM phase image indicate the randomly distributed GNPs in parallel to fibre surface that are favorable for enhanced wear resistance (right, scale bars, 200 nm).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. (a) The friction displacement, S , of a single glass fibre over the surface of abrasive paper up to fibre breakage, shows that the epoxy/GNPs lead to significant increase up to 200%, and the epoxy coating would yield about 50% improvement. Insert: schematic drawing of the measuring system. (b) the force of kinetic friction, f_k , versus friction displacement, δ , revealing the removal of epoxy coating layer or residues of epoxy/GNPs during friction compare to the control glass fibre. Data represent mean (\pm s.d.). (c) Comparison of the AFM phase images of the glass fibre surfaces after sliding wear against the SiC paper for the control, the epoxy coated and GNPs/epoxy systems. Deep 'groove' like surface indicates abrasive wear over glass surface. (d) Crack tended to propagate away from the CNTs-rich interphase of CNTs-glass fibre reinforced epoxy model composite.

Fig. 4. The fractional resistance increase $\Delta R/R_0$ (blue) and linear regression (grey line) of an individual single GNP-glass fibre during uniaxial tensile stress (dashed line) up to the fibre fracture.

Fig. 5. Dependence of the fractional resistance increase $\Delta R/R_0$ with temperature for an individual single GNP-glass fibre or CNT-glass fibre in N_2 or epoxy resin (Insert). Without the non-monotonous temperature dependence of the resistance, the line (Insert) with almost linear relationship makes a hint of “water free” composite interphase during storage.